

RATE OF GLAUCOMA IN PENSION AGE CITIZENS (2023 in the example of the city of Urganch)

**Yuldashev Bakhrom Sabirjanevich¹, Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich²,
Ruzmetova Dilfuza Tulibaevna³, Rajapov Sarvar Safarboevich⁴**

Department of Pathomorphology, Urganch Branch, Tashkent Medical Academy,
associate professor¹.

Tashkent Medical Academy, Urganch branch, "Pathomorphology" department,
Ph.D².

Tashkent Medical Academy, Urganch branch, "Obstetrics and gynecology"
department, Ph.D³.

Assistant of the "Clinical anatomy and histology" department of Urganch branch of
the Tashkent Medical Academy⁴.

Relevance of the topic: According to the World Health Organization, there are 65 million blind patients on earth, and 19-20 percent of them are glaucoma patients. Early detection of the disease, its correct treatment and preventive measures are still an actual topic of ophthalmology.

This pain is a chronic developing eye disease. The disease is mainly caused by increased intraocular pressure. The cause of glaucoma is a decrease in the patient's vision due to a violation of the exchange of fluid in the eye, a violation of nutrition in the optic nerve fiber and eye tissue. If the disease is not treated in time, it is observed that the ability to see is irreparably reduced, even leading to blindness. This disease is one of the leading causes of irreversible blindness worldwide.

The causes of glaucoma in humans are still unknown. Currently, a number of factors that lead to the appearance and development of this eye disease have been identified. One of the main factors of susceptibility to the disease is a person's age.

Glaucoma occurs more often after the age of 35-40, and with increasing age the susceptibility to the disease increases.

Purpose of work: as the purpose of the work, the origin of the disease, the level of incidence, and the spread of the disease among citizens living in the city of Urganch, i.e., mostly of retirement age, were studied.

Results obtained: the results of the investigation showed that glaucoma was found mainly in pension age citizens, that is, in men over 65 years old, and in women over 60 years old. The occurrence of the disease at such an age was attributed to the fact that they did not go to check-ups every 6 months for the prevention of ophthalmological diseases, and did not take the medicines recommended by the medical staff on time. In addition, 3/1 part of the disease was evaluated as a hereditary disease.

Conclusions: In conclusion, it can be said that the disease in prevention, during work or study, the lamp should be on the left side of the person, the light should be sufficient and take a break of 10-15 minutes every hour;

Special exercises recommended for the eyes are very important, especially moving the eyes to one side and the opposite side in an imaginary circle on the surface of the wall, heart and lung disease attacks, diabetes, atherosclerosis of cerebral blood vessels, liver

diseases have a negative effect on the eyes. it is not recommended for the patient to stand still or sit for a long time with his neck or body bent.

Negative habits, i.e. alcohol consumption, smoking, drug addiction are not only a problem of life, but also cause the development of glaucoma. a walk is recommended.

In a rational diet, it is recommended to eat products containing beta-carotene, vitamin A (carrots, blueberries, parsley, etc.), as well as foods rich in group B vitamins.

Every patient should undergo an ophthalmologist examination every 3 and 6 months.

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